

ISSN(E): 2770-8125

EUROPEAN INTERNATIONAL
JOURNAL OF ADVANCED
RESEARCH AND INNOVATIONS

EIJARI

2026

www.innojournals.my.id/index.php/eijari

European International Journal of Advanced Research and Innovations

Volume 02, Issue 06

EDITORIAL BOARD:

Professor Emma Franke

Editor in Chief

Prof. Jo Coldwell-Neilson

Associate Editor In Chief Deakin University, Australia

Mr Mohd Helmy

Abd Wahab Universiti Tun Hussein Onn Malaysia, Malaysia

Shafi'i Muhammad Abdulhamid

Federal University Of Technology Minna, Nigeria., Nigeria

Dr Man Fung (Kelvin) Lo

The Chinese University Of Hong Kong, Hong Kong

Dr Ahmad Samed

Al-Adwan Al Ahliyya Amman University, Jordan

Waleed Alsabhan

Kacst, Saudi Arabia Yvonne Antonucci Widener University, United States

Prof. Orit Avidov Ungar

Achva Academic College & Open University Of Israel, Israel

Dr. Aslina Baharum

Universiti Malaysia Sabah, Malaysia

ANCIENT CRAFTS AND SOCIO-ECONOMIC PROCESSES IN CENTRAL ASIA

Botirov Javlonbek Tilavoldiyevich

Andijan State Technical Institute

Assistant of the Department of "Languages and Humanities".

Email: botirovjavlonbek24@gmail.com

Abstract: This article provides information about ancient socio-economic processes in Central Asia, as well as about ancient crafts. Information is also provided about the first handicraft products in the region.

Keywords: Ancient crafts, Central Asia, Ancient East, agriculture, Sapallitepa, Bronze, Metallurgy, pottery.

The history of Uzbekistan has deep roots and a rich cultural past. This history, which has developed over many millennia, is studied as the history of our ancestors and our people. Independence paved the way for fundamental spiritual renewal in the life of the Uzbek people. Large-scale reforms are being implemented in the socio-economic, scientific-educational, and cultural spheres of our country.

The first article of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, adopted in its new edition, states that "Uzbekistan is a sovereign, democratic, legal, social, and secular state with a republican form of government. The names of the state "Republic of Uzbekistan" and "Uzbekistan" mean the same thing" [2.3].

As an independent, sovereign state, Uzbekistan has taken an eternal place in world history. Under the conditions of peace, stability, and harmony, national development, and a deep understanding of the essence of independence, we must continue to develop, on new foundations, the aspiration for creation in the history of our people, examples of patriotism, the unparalleled courage and noble, creative work of our great ancestors. Through the science of history, the causes and essence of the emergence of humanity, the features of the development of primitive society, the development of material and spiritual culture, the emergence of civilization, ethno-cultural processes, periodic changes in socio-economic and political relations, and many other events are studied. The history of Uzbekistan is an integral part of world history. One common geographical region—Central Asia—united neighboring tribes and peoples who lived there since ancient times through close cultural, socio-economic processes, mutual relations, and common cultural and ethnic roots. Central Asia is one of the centers of world civilization and the history of human culture [1.8].

It is known from history that as a result of the development of early humans, such types of farming as agriculture, animal husbandry, and craftsmanship also developed. Through these types of economy, one can obtain information about the

life, lifestyle, and occupations of early humans. Through this information, we can obtain more accurate information about our ancient ancestors.

In the Bronze Age, Central Asia became one of the important cultural centers of the Ancient East. Agriculture developed in the favorable geographical conditions of river oases was based on artificial irrigation. In the vicinity of ancient settlements, irrigated lands occupied vast areas. The methods of draining canals from rivers developed significantly, and the irrigated economy of the Bronze Age differed significantly from primitive agriculture, which was based on plowing. Alongside agriculture, livestock grazing on oasis meadows, as well as in foothill and steppe pastures, played an important role in people's lives. Bones of sheep, goats, and cows have been found in the settlements. For example, about 16,000 animal bones were found and examined in Sopollitepa. Most of them are sheep and goat bones, while others are camel and cow bones. At the same time, hunting wild birds and animals has not lost its significance in human life. This is confirmed by the remains of deer, gazelle, kulan, wild boar, rabbit, duck, pigeon, and many other animals and birds found at Sopollitepa. Hunting was a supplementary occupation for humans. They mainly hunted wild boar, deer, and kulan.

At this time, the foundations for the development of primitive crafts began to appear. During this period, our ancient ancestors began to attach special importance to metals in craftsmanship. This increased the demand for metal and metal products in handicrafts. Raw material deposits were essential for the development of metallurgy. Ancient copper mines and ore smelting kilns dating back to the Bronze Age have been discovered and studied in the Kyzylkum. In the Bronze Age, with the widespread spread of metalworking and significant changes in the methods of producing tools, people were forced to search for new copper deposits (especially after learning how to smelt copper with tin and lead). However, in the Early Metallurgical Period, copper was a valuable material, and pure copper was found only in certain places. In addition to the development of new lands, the dispersal of tribes into distant regions was associated with the discovery of copper, tin, and lead deposits.

As a result of these processes, processes such as population dispersal and settlement in raw material regions occurred. Of course, these processes played an important role in the development of early craftsmanship. Bronze Age artifacts testify to the high level of development of domestic craftsmanship alongside specialized crafts. People made various objects from clay, bone, stone, wood, and leather. During this period, clothing was woven from wool and flax. Ceramic and stone spindles used in the textile industry were found in the settlements. Large-scale changes occurred in the social life of the population based on the development of productive farms and craftsmanship. Agriculture and animal husbandry played a key role in regulating the exchange of surplus products and goods.

Collective dwellings studied in Bronze Age settlements, gold jewelry, bronze vessels and weapons found in rich burials, necklaces made of precious stones, and personal tamgas of clan leaders provide information about changes in social relations.

The property of large patriarchal families consisted of dwellings, handicraft products, agricultural products, and livestock. Pottery and bronze products became products of trade. There are various views and approaches to the topic of socio-economic relations of the Bronze Age. Since written sources on this issue are unknown, it is more likely that land ownership, the use of pastures, water sources, and irrigation facilities in the Bronze Age region had a public significance than private ownership. It is doubtful that the land was legally registered as private property during this period. In conclusion, it should be noted that socio-economic processes have been developing in Central Asia since ancient times. Therefore, a large population has lived in these regions since ancient times. As a result of these processes, unique types of ancient crafts have developed in this region. It is precisely these processes that serve as the basis for the types of national crafts in the region today.

REFERENCES USED:

1. Sagdullayev A.S. va boshqalar. O‘zbekiston tarixi I kitob (Eng qadimgi davrdan –XIV asr o‘rtalarigacha) T.: 2024.
2. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Konstitutsiyasi, T.: 2023
3. Farg‘ona vodiysi qishloq aholisining hunarmandchilik an‘analari.Z.Esonov. Farg‘ona. 2023
4. Z.Nosirova Farg‘ona vodiysi badiiy hunarmandchiligi// Moziydan sado.- 2014.N:2(62).
5. Saodat Omonova “O‘zbek an‘anaviy hunarmandchiligi tarixiy jarayonlar kontekstida”Toshkent.:“Yangi asr”, 2018. B. 217
6. A.Maxmudov. Dissertatsiya. “Farg‘ona vodiysi milliy pichoqchilik maktablariningshakllanish tarixi va rivojlanish bosqichlari”. – Farg‘ona. 2024.